

DIGITAL ETHIC FOR YOUNG CITIZEN: CASE IN INDONESIA

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ABSTRACT

The issues of digital ethics are important and interesting to be discussed when the digital world has developed widely and has become life style and need to be always connected to one another. The young citizens have become internet users who are susceptible to violate the digital world ethics due to their misunderstanding that they interact with real people in other network. It is not only letters on monitor, but also the real human characters. This research applied qualitative approach using in-depth interview and observation in using social media among the young generation, which is the students of senior high school in Malang. The research findings revealed that they knowledge regarding the function and benefits of technology is sufficient, in which they are capable to use various social media such as Facebook, twitter, instagram, etc. In addition, the students of senior high school in Malang are also considered as internet generation, where internet has provided opportunities for them to learn digital skills and norms. The more they are involved in online communities, the more they develop by defining their interest. In addition, they are also able to interact and have a collaboration with certain group.

Keywords: Ethic, digital ethic, young citizen, Indonesia

Social media allows its users to carry out various activities, including consuming as well as participating in making, commenting, and sharing various contents. In addition, the users of social media can also build a conversation and community through the social media because it makes the people with the same interest easier to meet.

Based on the report issued by We are Social (2022) on the data of internet and social media use in Indonesia, there were 191 million active users of social media in January 2022. Such amount increased by 12.35% compared to the previous year of 170 million people. This trend indicates that the social media users in Indonesia continuously increase every year. However, this growth experienced fluctuation since 2014 to 2022. In this case, the highest increase of social media users was 34.2% in 2017, yet it slowed down until 6.3% in the previous year. Furthermore, the rate increased again this year. Among the social media used in Indonesia, WhatsApp becomes the most used social media by Indonesian people. It was reported that the percentage of its users reached 88.7%. It is then followed by Instagram and Facebook whose percentage reached 84.8% and 81.3%, respectively. Meanwhile, the proportion of the users of TikTok and Telegram is 63.1% and 62.8%, respectively.

Media presents in public space, hence all people can access it in terms that “communication is not distorted”, in which democracy in public is where the individuals interact to each other and build democracy based on awareness (Habermas, 1984). Regarding the relationship between

the news media users in internet, Reichert & Print (2017) revealed through their research that news media users trigger discussion concerning civics issues, although different media provides different effects.

Social media indeed gives more negative effects than positive effects (Woods & Scott, 2016). The reason is because students tend to spend their time on social media for purpose other than education, hence it possibly causes disruption in learning environment and affects their advance in academic (Bekalu et al., 2019; Mahdiuon et al., 2019; Woods & Scott, 2016). Furthermore, spending much time on social network can cause sedentary life style and decrease in daily physical activities, which further can lead to the users susceptible to non-communicable diseases including obesity, diabetes, and hypertension (Hu et al., 2001; Melkevik et al., 2015; Zou et al., 2019). In addition, the use of social media also has negative effects on mental health, thus causing depression and anxiety (Woods & Scott, 2016). Therefore, due to the increased amount of typical sites and high demand of social media among university students, it is necessary to review the purpose of using social network site.

Social media can bring both positive and negative effects for its users when there is no digital ethic as the filter. The digital world has led to the production of several regulations regarding the appropriate and inappropriate behavior for the digital communities and how individual as the digital community members should behave (inside and outside the school), since it has become an issue for the parents and the society as a whole. Since the school and society has been overwhelmed by the digital technology, a structure that teaches the students to behave in such technological era is necessary (Ribble & Bailey, 2007).

One of the worrying things is the emerging of various cases due to the effect of intolerant social media. Duel between students occurred in one of the regions in Indonesia due to a trivial problem of mocking each other in social media of Facebook that leads to fight on Thursday night 14 March of 2019 (Kompas, 18/3/2019).

A digital forum community has certain rules and regulations that discuss limitation and the best method in using internet facilities (Pane, 2016). In the case of digital world, we also acknowledge internet label or commonly known as netiquette, which is a label for interaction using the internet. The most important thing in netiquette is that we must always aware that we interact with real people in other network, not merely letters on monitor, but the real human character (Pane, 2016).

According to the background stated above, current research discussed the perception of the youth on social media and digital ethic on the youth.

METHOD

This research applied qualitative research method because the issues raised are related to the fundamental concept of human that depends on the observation. According to (J. Creswell, 2015a), qualitative research aims to understand the social phenomenon of the participants. Furthermore, phenomenological approach was also implemented through qualitative method, which mainly focuses on life experience of certain community. The basic objective of this

research is to describe (illustrate) a certain phenomenon characteristic (J. Creswell, 2015b). Therefore, the analysis technique applied in this research is certainly qualitative analysis, which is by reviewing the data, organizing the data, selecting the data to be processed, as well as finding the data so that it can become information. In accordance with the approach applied in this research, the research data employed were collected through interview, observation, documentation, and field notes as an encouraging step of the research results (J. W. Creswell, 2016). In this case, the research participants involved were students. Meanwhile, the analysis technique applied five steps, including making an expression list of participants' response answer, reduction and elimination of expression, making cluster, validation on the expression, and exposure of the expression (Moustakas, 1994).

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Research results on digital ethic on the senior high school students in Malang City are concerning (1) the level of knowledge in social media, (2) social media as entertainment, education, and information facilities, and (3) capabilities in mastering digital ethic.

In this case, the level of knowledge of the senior high school students in Malang can be seen based on (1) students' ownership of social media account, (2) students' ownership of various social media (Instagram, Facebook, twitter, tik tok, and YouTube), as well as (3) the posting of daily activities in social media. Based on the results of the interview that was carried out by 18 students of senior high school in Malang City, almost all of the students have social media account. In this case, Instagram is the social media mostly owned and used by the students. Meanwhile, the remaining are Twitter, Facebook, TikTok, and YouTube accounts.

Most of the students utilized social media to post their daily life in their social media account. In this case, most of them posted their daily life on Instagram and Facebook. In addition, they also posted their activities on their Tik Tok account. Therefore, it can be concluded that social media is used for social interaction, where in the communication world; social media is useful as a facility to build relationship. Moreover, social media also assists us to have a long distance communication because social media has global reach. Hence, social media makes it easier for us to interact wherever we are.

Entertainment media: many social media types have been currently entertainment media, one of them is YouTube. In this case, we can find any entertainment, starting from funny stories to funny pictures. We can find many interesting things in social network to entertain us.

Information media: we can post recent news through internet network to help us in obtaining information. This does not only include news, but also other information that can be used as knowledge media.

Discovering creativities: we can use various social media to discover our creativity and to express ourselves, for example writing articles or various experiences on blog.

Based on the observation results on the students' account, it was found that the students of senior high school used social media to post their daily activities, including in the social

environment, school, and family. In addition, several students also posted their hobbies, personal stories, game, and pet. Furthermore, students also utilized social media as a promotion tool of their extracurricular activities at school. In this case, there is one interesting thing found, in which students from millennial generation are active in using social media, particularly in Instagram story, while limiting themselves in posting on the Instagram account post. It was found that several Instagram accounts of the students have zero post. Based on the interview, an interesting fact discovered that they think posts must be in accordance with the condition of the times, so when they post something, it only applied for a month, and then archived because they considered them not feasible to be posted.

The students of senior high school in Malang used social media as an entertainment, education, and information facilities. This can be seen based on the interview results that students used the social media well as an entertainment facility, such as Instagram, twitter, tiktok, or youtube. In addition, the students of senior high school in Malang also used social media as an education facility, seen from the posts made by Instagram accounts of: @falizahanifa32 who posted about drum band activities at school, @ddsyya who posted activities at school, and @siskaalia who also posted activities at school. Meanwhile, social media as an information facility was utilized by tiktok account of @pazelzkies who gave game information and Instagram account of @ahmadzulfikar26 who gave information about cat.

Critical Thinking and Problem Solving characterizes Civics learning

Research results showed that the students of senior high school in Malang has capabilities in using technology, in which they are capable in using their social media as a learning source well. This was proven by the students of senior high school in Malang who can design and develop learning experience and assessment manually and digitally by integrating various learning tools and sources that are relevant to encourage the students so that they have higher thinking skill and become more creative (Lance Bennett, 2017). The description above becomes the researchers' support in the research results that students have ethics in using digital tools. Therefore, they can be an example for the other students or their peer in using technology correctly in teaching and learning process, designing strategy, and implementing technology-based learning, aiming to develop the students' abilities in building their independent characteristics to formulate their learning sources (Barassi, 2019a).

It is also supported by the statement that giving opportunities to the students to participate in formulating learning process will strengthen the students' digital characters (Flores & Carrie James, 2020). Therefore, it needs a good learning model. (Munir, 2017) in his book stated that in order to achieve certain learning objective, educator must use a learning model. In this case, a learning model related to the 21st century skills learning is meaningful learning, active learning, direct learning, indirect learning, and distance learning.

Furthermore, this research results also indicate that the development of digital-based learning model also needs a strategy. **The Strategy of Implementing 21st Century Skills Learning Model to Develop Citizenship Characters in Malang.** Therefore, based on the description above, building the young generation characters through 21st century skills learning is very

important. Hence, character building can be done systematically and sustainable by involving the aspects of knowledge, feeling, loving, and acting (Barassi, 2019b). Current research discovered the good ethics in using technology are; first Instruction should be student centered, second education should be collaborative, third learning should have contest, and four school should be integrated with the society. In this case, students must be the center of learning and subject instead of the object. Students must also learn to have a collaboration with other people. In addition, teacher must teach a meaningful learning for the students so that the students can carry out their real daily life in national and state life (Williams et al., 2016a)

Furthermore, Civics Education as one of the subjects that conduct mission to build a good and smart citizen characters for each level of education, hence civics need a learning concept that provides characters and implementation integrated with the values of implementing technology and Pancasila. In addition, the learning concept of civics must also be nuanced on learning renewal and innovation with the main aim of students' skills. Therefore, the results of the current research indicated that the students of senior high school in Malang has a very strong responsibility and critical thinking. This is supported by the presence of curriculum development that directs to such skills that can be described further as follow:

As one of renewal forms in the implementation of civics education in this research, the students of senior high school in Malang has been able to integrate the civics material into parts of global issue. This is supported by the findings that civics education as a renewal in technology development has a main material of a learning material that indicates to global education (Brush, 2018). Other research projects also showed that the learning habit of the students of senior high school in Malang has made technology as a part of a good learning pattern. This is a positive value that needs to be preserved, where in fact many current generations often used technology for purpose other than learning, instead they used it for negative things. It is proven by the analysis that was carried out by the researchers recently.

Table 1.1 Research conducted by Ministry of Communication and Information as well as Unicef

No	Findings	Description
1.	About 30 million children and adolescents in Indonesia that used internet and digital media.	About 80% of the data were internet users and there was a proof showing a strong digital gap between them.
2.	This research is a first research project that has data uniqueness on the group of children and adolescents that have never been used internet	This research project found a very visible gap on urban children and adolescents by 13% who did not use internet, while 87% was the remaining
3.	This research found that the majority of them were online media users for more than a year.	This research found that 69% of the respondents used computer to access the internet, 52% used mobile phone to access the internet, and 21% used the smartphone to access the internet.

Source: Processed by the Researchers

Based on the table above, the deviation and opportunity of the students, including the young citizens, are seen on the gap of technology and internet use. This research is further supported by previous research (Feriyansyah, 2015) that young citizens are instrument toward global citizens. The research also found that advance in technology make changes in the interaction patterns of the citizens. It is realized in the implementation of their daily life which depends on the technology, so that in order to control the citizens to stay in the corridor of national characters, government, through the education, needs to optimize the civics concept in encountering the digital era”.

The facts above also bring effect on the implementation of education that has been integrated with the technology, where changes in technology development will significantly affect the education planning and implementation. Therefore, update on the learning approach that is in accordance with the needs and up-to-date of the current generation condition is needed (Pritchard et al., 2018).

Furthermore, based on the results of the research that has been conducted on the senior high school students in Malang in utilizing technology by the young generation as students has made changes in their way of thinking, their learning method that must be in accordance with the technology needs, thus students must formulate an interesting technology-based learning method and strategy”. The behavior of the young generation that is very dependent on the technology requires them to do their task using technology-based learning facilities, in this case is online learning (Gauthier, 2020)

Another finding of this research found that senior high school students in Malang had positive learning habits, indicating that (Bowyer & Kahne, 2020a) ”civics education that is taught through technology will form students’ habit that are able to conduct social control in their environment, which further affects the advance of civics practice”.

Therefore, the above statement is supported by another perception (Bowyer & Kahne, 2020b) that the digital life of the digital generation becomes an information center for the young citizens to obtain political and social information. Hence, social interaction of the citizens cannot be separated from their digital life. In addition, previous statement (David Finkelhor, 2020) also revealed that internet is a place for the young citizens to hear and share their perception and opinion, because the young generation is more active in online life, and they can express themselves freely according to their identity in digital life. David also added that the young generation is also able to form digital community and life based on their need.

The 21st century has two decades and known as knowledge age, as explained previously by Mukhadis (2013) that current life is based on good knowledge in education, social empowering, economic, and industry (Heiss & Matthes, 2019).

Following the learning trend of the 21st century, the development of individual skill of the senior high school students is also needed. The demand for the individual in 21st century is that individual must master both hard skill and soft skill so that when they enter the working world, they have prepared themselves to compete with people from other country. “The core subjects and interdisciplinary 21st century themes are surrounded by three sets of skills most in demand

in the 21st century: (i) learning and innovation skills, (ii) information, media and technology skills, (iii) life and career skills” (Trilling and Fadel, 2009)

In accordance with the skills explained above, Assessment and Teaching for 21st Century Skills (ATCS) concluded four main things related to the 21st century skills, those are way of thinking, way of working, working tool, and life skills. In this case, way of thinking includes creative thinking, problem solving, decision-making, and learning (Muchsini & Siswandari, 2018).

Therefore, the 21st century skill is an expectation that must present in 2013 curriculum, although not all schools implement 2013 curriculum because many factors inhibit its implementation. Through the existing curriculum, we are required to have wide insight and capabilities in using technology because the advance of technology allows all things become faster, even the human power becomes less used since all things have been controlled by sophisticated technology (Williams et al., 2016b).

CONCLUSION

The students of senior high school in Malang are able to use technology media wisely, where they are able to control themselves to use social media as an entertainment facility and learning source.

The utilization of social media carried out by the students of senior high school in Malang indicates that their knowledge is sufficient on using the function and benefits of technology, where they are able to use various social media such as Facebook, twitter, instagram, etc.

The students of senior high school in Malang can also be considered internet generation, in which internet provides opportunities for them to learn digital skill and norms. The more they are involved in online community, the more they develop by defining their interest as well as interacting and having a collaborating with certain groups.

This correlates with the current research in the case that civics education takes a role as a learning source that utilizes digital media to develop citizenship, involvement, and self-development in the young citizens. In this case, learning that is conducted through digital media can grow the digital literacy of the young citizens as well encourage the political activities in online form, etc.

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